

Modelling and Simulating Particle Transport in Liquid Composite Moulding Processes

The 24th International Conference on Composite Materials (ICCM24)

6th August 2025, Baltimore, USA

Shanthar Rajinth

Department of Materials, The University of Manchester, United Kingdom

Center for Composite Materials, University of Delaware, USA

rajinth.shanthar@manchester.ac.uk

Supervised by

Dr. Robert Prosser, Prof. Prasad Potluri, Dr. Pavel Simacek, Prof. Suresh G. Advani, Dr. Chamil Abeykoon

1 Introduction

- 1.1 RTM Process Overview
- 1.2 Particle Mixed Resin Flow

2 Methodology

- 2.1 Resin Flow Model
- 2.2 Particle Transport Models
- 2.3 Numerical Implementation
- 2.4 Particles and Permeability
- 2.5 Numerical Flow Domain

3 Results

- 3.1 Partially Coupled Model
- 3.2 Fully Coupled Model
- 3.3 Time Evolution of Particle Distribution
- 3.4 Time Evolution of Permeability
- 3.5 Influence of Particle Injection Conditions
- 3.6 Influence of Particle Size
- 3.7 Trials with Radial Flow

4 Summary and Outlook

1. Introduction

1.1. RTM Process Overview

- Resin Transfer Moulding (RTM) is a process used to manufacture Fibre Reinforced Polymers (FRP), which consists of 5 steps as shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: The Resin Transfer Moulding (RTM) process

1. Introduction

1.2. Particle Mixed Resin Flow

- Particles may be mixed with the resin to improve the properties of parts manufactured using RTM [1][2].
- The sizes of these particles can range from the micrometre scale to the nanometre scale, as shown in Fig. 2.
- Transport models and simulations can provide valuable information regarding the final particle distribution, permeability changes, and particle filtration [3].
- The presence of particles will affect the permeability of the flow channels, which in turn will affect the flow of particles [4][5].

Figure 2: Different types of particles (a) Multi-Walled Carbon Nanotubes (b) Graphene Nanoplatelets [6]

2. Methodology

2.1. Resin Flow Model

- The resin flow through the reinforcement preform is modelled as a flow through a porous medium, governed by the mass conservation equation (Eq. 1) and the Darcy equation (Eq. 2).

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\mathbf{u} = -\frac{\mathbf{K}}{\mu} \nabla P \quad (2)$$

- Here, \mathbf{u} is the volume-averaged resin velocity, \mathbf{K} is the permeability tensor for the porous preform, μ is the resin viscosity, and P is the resin pressure.
- The above equations can be combined to obtain Eq. 3, which is then used to solve for the in-mould pressure distribution at each time step.

$$\nabla \cdot \left(\frac{\mathbf{K}}{\mu} \nabla P \right) = 0 \quad (3)$$

2. Methodology

2.2. Particle Transport Models

Partially Coupled Model

- In this approach, the preform permeability is assumed to be constant and unaffected by the presence of particles (Fig. 3a)
- After the pressure and velocity fields are solved, the particle locations are updated based on the resin flow, resulting in a passive transport.

Fully Coupled Model

- In this approach, the preform permeability is updated at each time step according to the presence of particles within an element (Fig. 3b)
- The new permeabilities of elements are calculated using the Gebart model by adjusting the porosity accordingly.

Figure 3a: Partially coupled model

Figure 3b: Fully coupled model

2. Methodology

2.3. Numerical Implementation

- Resin pressure and velocity values are calculated using the Liquid Injection Moulding Simulation (LIMS) software developed at the University of Delaware.
- The particle transportation is implemented using a worker script that reads pressure and velocity data from LIMS and updates the particle location.
- This architecture is shown in Fig. 4 [7].
- At each time step, Eq. 3 is solved using the finite element method in LIMS.

$$\nabla \cdot \left(\frac{K}{\mu} \nabla P \right) = 0 \quad (3)$$

- Data is communicated between LIMS and the worker script using Message Passing Interface (MPI).

Figure 4:
Simulation software architecture [7]

2. Methodology

2.4. Particles and Permeability

- In the fully coupled model, the new permeabilities of elements are calculated using the Gebart model for transverse permeability of cylinders in quadratic arrangement, given in Eq. 4 [8].

$$K_{\perp} = \frac{16}{9\pi\sqrt{2}} \left(\sqrt{\frac{V_{fmax}}{V_f}} - 1 \right)^{5/2} R^2 \quad (4)$$

- Here, V_{fmax} is the maximum volume fraction, V_f is the volume fraction, R is the fibre radius.

- The volume fraction is updated according to the number of particles within an element, as shown in Fig. 5a.

- As more particles enter the element, the permeability gradually reduces (Fig. 5b) and becomes zero beyond the maximum fraction.

Figure 5: (a) Contents within an element (b) Variation of permeability with the number of particles within an element

2. Methodology

2.5. Numerical Flow Domain

- The numerical domain is a 10cmx30cm rectangular mould, and the resin is injected under controlled pressure from a line gate, as shown in Fig. 6.
- Particles are introduced to the system from the inlet at different concentrations and pressures, and their motion is tracked.
- The numerical parameters are given in Table 1.

Figure 6: Numerical domain setup

Table 1: Flow simulation parameters

Parameter	Value
Preform permeability	5e-11 m ²
Resin viscosity	200 mPas
Injection pressure	25 kPa
Mould thickness	5 mm
Particle diameter	0.6 mm

3. Results

3.1. Partially Coupled Model

- During the simulation, 1710 particles were introduced into the system.
- Fig. 7a shows the path of motion of the particles.
- The particles move in straight lines due to being passively transported by the flow.
- Fig. 7b shows the distribution of the particles within the mould at fill time.
- The injection profile of the particles is preserved due to the absence of flow obstructions.

Figure 7a

Figure 7b

3. Results

3.2. Fully Coupled Model

- During the simulation, 2052 particles were introduced into the system.
- Fig. 8a shows the path of motion of the particles.
- Now, their flow paths are affected due to the local changes in permeability.
- Fig. 8b shows the distribution of the particles within the mould at fill time.
- Near the inlet, particles accumulate causing the permeability to reduce, leading to further accumulation.

Figure 8a

Figure 8b

3. Results

3.3. Time Evolution of Particle Distribution

(a) $t = 100$ s

(b) $t = 500$ s

(c) $t = 2000$ s

(d) Mould fill

Figure 9: Evolution of the particle distribution with time

3. Results

3.4. Time Evolution of Permeability

(a) $t = 0$ s

(b) $t = 500$ s

(c) $t = 2000$ s

(d) $t = \text{Mould fill}$

Figure 10: Evolution of the domain permeability with time

3. Results

3.5. Influence of Particle Injection Conditions – Inlet Pressure

- The effect of inlet pressure on the final distribution of particles was investigated.
- The particle inlet concentration was fixed, and the results are given in Fig. 11.

(a) 12.5 kPa inlet pressure

(b) 25 kPa inlet pressure

(c) 50 kPa inlet pressure

Figure 11: Variation of final particle distribution with inlet pressure

3. Results

3.5. Influence of Particle Injection Conditions – Injection Rate

- The effect of injection rate on the final distribution of particles was also investigated.
- The results are analogous to those obtained for varying inlet pressure previously, as shown in Fig. 12.

(a) 1 particle per second

(b) 1 particle per 2 seconds

(c) 1 particle per 4 seconds

Figure 12: Variation of final particle distribution with particle injection rate

3. Results

3.6. Influence of Particle Size

- The particle size influences the rate of permeability reduction, as shown in Fig. 13.
- Larger particle sizes result in a rapid permeability reduction, leading to early particle accumulation and blockage (Fig. 13c).

(a) $r = 0.4$ mm

(b) $r = 0.6$ mm

(c) $r = 0.8$ mm

Figure 13: Variation of final particle distribution with particle size

3. Results

3.7. Trials with Radial Flow

- Particle transport via radial flow across a 2D mould was also investigated, where particles were introduced randomly.

Figure 14: Radial flow geometry

Figure 15: Particle evolution with time

3. Results

3.7. Trials with Radial Flow

- The influence of injection rate and particle size on the final particle distribution was investigated.
- Similar to the linear flow, high injection rates resulted in particle accumulation and blockages near the inlet (Fig. 16) .

Figure 16: Variation of final particle distribution with injection rate

3. Results

3.7. Trials with Radial Flow

- The influence of injection rate and particle size on the final particle distribution was investigated.
- Similar to the linear flow, high injection rates resulted in particle accumulation and blockages near the inlet (Fig. 16) .
- This was also the case for larger particle sizes (Fig. 17).

Figure 17: Variation of final particle distribution with particle size

4. Summary and Outlook

- The transport of finite particles during resin impregnation was modelled and simulated using LIMS and MPI.
- Pressure and velocity fields are solved using LIMS, and these are used by a worker script to transport the particles.
- Updated permeabilities computed by the worker were sent back to LIMS, allowing fully coupled simulations.
- The influence of inlet pressure, injection rate, particle size and mould geometry were investigated.
- Simulating flow through further complex 3D mould geometries with varying particle sizes need to be explored.
- Particle mobility needs to be modelled and incorporated into the programme.

References

- [1] J. Barroeta Robles *et al.*, ‘Processing and properties of graphene-enhanced glass fibre composites using a scalable manufacturing process’, *Composite Structures*, vol. 267, p. 113874, Jul. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.compstruct.2021.113874.
- [2] B. M. Louis, J. Maldonado, F. Klunker, and P. Ermanni, ‘Particle distribution from in-plane resin flow in a resin transfer molding process’, *Polymer Engineering & Science*, vol. 59, no. 1, pp. 22–34, 2019, doi: 10.1002/pen.24860.
- [3] Y. Djebara, A. Imad, A. Saouab, and T. Kanit, ‘A numerical modelling for resin transfer molding (RTM) process and effective thermal conductivity prediction of a particle-filled composite carbon–epoxy’, *Journal of Composite Materials*, vol. 55, no. 1, pp. 3–15, Jan. 2021, doi: 10.1177/0021998320940035.
- [4] W. R. Hwang, S. G. Advani, and S. Walsh, ‘Direct simulations of particle deposition and filtration in dual-scale porous media’, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, vol. 42, no. 10, pp. 1344–1352, 2011.
- [5] M. Chohra, S. G. Advani, A. Gokce, and S. Yarlagadda, ‘Modeling of filtration through multiple layers of dual scale fibrous porous media’, *Polymer Composites*, vol. 27, no. 5, pp. 570–581, 2006, doi: 10.1002/pc.20228.
- [6] C. M. Long, M. A. Nascarella, and P. A. Valberg, ‘Carbon black vs. black carbon and other airborne materials containing elemental carbon: Physical and chemical distinctions’, *Environmental Pollution*, vol. 181, pp. 271–286, Oct. 2013, doi: 10.1016/j.envpol.2013.06.009.
- [7] P. Simacek, N. Niknafs Kermani, and S. G. Advani, ‘Coupled Process Modeling of Flow and Transport Phenomena in LCM Processing’, *Integr Mater Manuf Innov*, vol. 11, no. 3, pp. 363–381, Sep. 2022, doi: 10.1007/s40192-022-00268-1.
- [8] B. R. Gebart, ‘Permeability of Unidirectional Reinforcements for RTM’, *Journal of Composite Materials*, vol. 26, no. 8, pp. 1100–1133, Aug. 1992, doi: 10.1177/002199839202600802.

Thank You

Q&A